

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**STATUS OF CARRIES AND ORAL HYGIENE IN THE GROUP
OF CHILDREN WITH CLEFT LIP AND PALATE CHILDREN****Dr Aswa Aslam Chaudhry¹, Dr. Ikram Manzoor², Dr Shazia Tanveer³**¹ Margalla Institute of Health Sciences, Rawalpindi., ² Shaheed Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto Medical University, Islamabad., ³ Dental Surgeon, THQ hospital Mankera Distt Bhakkar.**Article Received:** October 2020 **Accepted:** November 2020 **Published:** December 2020**Abstract:****Aim:** The aim of the study was to determine the prevalence of caries and oral hygiene in a group of children with cleft lip and palate (CLP).**Place and Duration:** This study was conducted in Margalla Dental Hospital, Rawalpindi for one-year duration from August 2019 to August 2020.**Methods:** A total of 84 children with cleft (45 men and 39 women) were examined for caries and oral hygiene. Children were divided into two age groups; Group A with children from one to six years old and group B with children from seven to 14 years old. All children in both age groups had tooth decay.**Results:** The mean dmft score (decayed, missing and filled deciduous teeth) in children from group A was 10.54 (SD 4.59). In children from group B, the total mean DMFT / DMFT score (decayed, missing and filled deciduous and permanent teeth) was 10.92 (SD 4.90), respectively. No statistically significant ($p > 0.05$) difference was found between the mean DMFT / DMFT results depending on the age and sex of children with cleft. More than half (54.7%) of the children had poor oral hygiene.**Conclusion:** In conclusion; the incidence and severity of caries was high in children with clefts. Most of the children had poor oral hygiene.**Key words:** dental caries, oral hygiene, cleft lip and palate, children.**Corresponding author:****Dr. Aswa Aslam Chaudhry,**
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Please cite this article in press Aswa Aslam Chaudhry et al, **Status Of Carries And Oral Hygiene In The Group Of Children With Cleft Lip And Palate Children.**, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(12).

INTRODUCTION:

Cleft lip (CL) and cleft palate (CP) are some of the most common congenital malformations seen after birth¹⁻². A cleft lip is the result of a failure in the normal lip fusion process that has come to an end in embryonic life. The cleft lip can be unilateral or bilateral and can range from a slight noticeable scar to a complete slit through the nose. A cleft palate is an opening in the roof of the mouth (palate) caused by the palatal shelves not fully converging on both sides of the mouth and connecting with each other. Cleft lip and palate (CLP) causes immediate and urgent feeding problems. The cleft lip creates sucking problems during feeding, while the cleft palate makes it very difficult to suck; milk or food may leak from the infant's nose instead of being swallowed [3-4]. The cleft lip and palate often exist together. Both conditions appear at different times during pregnancy, and the exact etiology is unknown. However, both of these conditions are attributed to developmental and growth problems in early pregnancy. Other factors such as heredity, environmental influences during pregnancy, blood supply, radiation exposure, severe vitamin deficiencies, certain medications, and biochemical processes can also affect the human fetus [5-6]. Only two epidemiological studies have found the occurrence of facial cleft in Pakistan. Kumar *et al.* (1991) in a hospital study reported the incidence of 0.3 per 1000 live births over a six-year period in Pakistan. In another hospital study, Bokar *et al.* (1993) reported the incidence of 2.19 clefts per 1,000 live births in India. Cleft Children often have problems with aesthetics, speech, hearing, feeding and swallowing, as well as poor dentition. A review of the literature provides only a few studies that have assessed the incidence of caries in children with clefts. Lauterstein and Mendelsohn (1964) 8 found no significant difference between the experience of caries in children with and without a cleft in Sweden. Johnsen and Dixon (1984) found more carious lesions in the milk incisors of children with a cleft than children without a cleft in the UK. Two other relatively newer studies in the UK found that more than half of the children with clefts were free from caries, which is attributed to strict preventive dental care for these children⁷. Researchers in other countries report more carious, filled and missing teeth in children with clefts compared to children without clefts, and concluded that children with clefts had a higher risk of developing tooth decay than normal children of a similar age group. A study on the prevalence of caries in school and preschool children in Pakistan has shown a high prevalence of caries. However, such a study has not been conducted in children with clefts. Only a few studies have been published on periodontal health in children with clefts

[8-9]. Overall, periodontal disease of varying severity is common in children with clefts. Various studies have found that children with clefts exhibited poor oral hygiene as well as poorer gum health. Despite an established relationship between gum / periodontal health and poor oral hygiene, no information is available on the oral hygiene status of children with clefts. Therefore, the aim of the presented research was to determine the experience of caries and the state of oral hygiene in split children.

METHODOLOGY:

Children with cleft lip and palate admitted in Margalla Dental Hospital, Rawalpindi for one-year duration from August 2019 to August 2020 were included. These children were screened for caries and oral hygiene during routine visits to CLP clinics, with parental consent. Children are classified into three categories according to the type of cleft; CL only, CP only, and CLP children. The children were examined by three examiners in a dental chair with a dental mirror and an explorer. Credibility between investigators and between patients was determined by the Kappa method and all were considered excellent (0.9 and above). The data obtained during the study was recorded on a form specially designed for the study. The following indicators were used to assess caries and oral hygiene in children. WHO criteria were used to diagnose dental caries. Caries was diagnosed on the basis of visual evidence after drying and removing debris from the teeth with the help of an investigator and a mirror. No x-rays were taken. The study used the oral hygiene index described by James *et al.* The index covers three categories of tooth cleanliness. - Good: the teeth are clean. There is no trace of food debris or alba matter. - Poor: the teeth are very dirty. Fair: This class falls between the two preceding ones. There is some evidence of debris, but not of the degree recognized as poor. The data was then entered into a computer using FOXPRO software and analyzed using the Social Science Statistics Program (SPSS) version # 19. Different frequencies were generated. The Pearson Chi-square test was used to determine the gender differences in relation to caries and oral hygiene, and any significant relationship between dental caries and oral hygiene.

RESULTS:

A total of 84 children with cleft, 45 men and 39 women with an average age of 6.6 (SD 3.7) years were examined in the study. There were 48 children in group A and 36 children in group B. Of the 84 children tested, 29 (34.5%) had CL, 27 (32.1%) had CP, and 28 (33.4%) had CLP.

TABLE 1: DISTRIBUTION OF CHILDREN BY GENDER AND CLEFT TYPE.

Cleft Type	Male (%)	Female (%)	Total (%)
CL	15 (51.7)	14 (48.3)	29 (34.5)
CP	10 (37.0)	17 (63.0)	27 (32.1)
CLP	20 (71.4)	8 (28.6)	28 (33.4)
Total	45 (53.6)	39 (46.4)	84 (100)

Table 1 summarizes the distribution of children by sex and cleft type. There was no difference in caries experience or in oral hygiene status for cleft categories, therefore pooled data are presented. Children were divided into two age groups; Group A consisted of children aged one to six, and group B had children aged seven to 14. All children in both groups had tooth decay. The experience of caries in both groups is presented in Table 2.

TABLE 2: CARIES EXPERIENCE OF THE CHILDREN

Age Group	Mean dmft/DMFT (SD)	Mean decay (SD)	Mean missing (SD)	Mean filled (SD)
A	10.54 (4.59)*	9.23 (4.39)	1.17 (1.95)	0.15 (1.01)
B	10.92 (4.9)**	9.6 (4.77)	1.17 (1.94)	0.14 (1.01)

The mean DFT in children from group A was 10.54 (SD 4.59) with the caries component (d) 9.23 (SD 4.39), the missing (m) component 1, 17 (SD 1.95) and filled (f) component 0.15 (SD 1.01). In group B children; the mean score was 10.92 (SD 4.90) with the decay component 9.6 (SD 4.77), the missing component 1.17 (SD 1.94) and the filled component 0.14 (SD 1.01). There was no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) in mean caries scores depending on age. The mean caries scores were slightly higher in female children compared to male children (Table 3). However, the difference did not reach statistical significance ($p > 0.05$).

TABLE 3: CARIES EXPERIENCE OF THE CHILDREN IN RELATION TO GENDER

Age Group	Gender	Mean dmft/DMFT	SD	p value
1-6 Years	Male	9.96	4.11	>0.05
	Female	11.23	5.12	
> 6 Years	Male	5.32	4.60	>0.05
	Female	6.00	5.72	

Very few children (6%) had good oral hygiene, and the vast majority (94.0%) of the children had good or poor oral hygiene (Table 4). There was no statistically significant difference ($p > 0.05$) between the oral hygiene status and the gender of children with cleft.

TABLE 4: ORAL HYGIENE STATUS IN RELATION TO GENDER

Gender	Oral hygiene			Total (%)
	Good (%)	Fair (%)	Poor (%)	
Male	4(8.9)	14(31.1)	27(60.0)	45(100.0)
Female	1(2.6)	19(48.7)	19(48.7)	39(100.0)
Total	5(6.0)	33(39.3)	46(54.7)	84(100.0)

Younger children with clefts had relatively better oral hygiene compared to the older group (Table 5). But; the difference was not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). There was no correlation ($p > 0.05$) between the experience of caries and the state of oral hygiene in both age groups.

TABLE 5: ORAL HYGIENE STATUS IN RELATION TO AGE

Gender	Oral hygiene			Total (%)
	Good (%)	Fair (%)	Poor (%)	
1-6 Years	4(8.3)	21 (43.8)	23(47.9)	48(100.0)
> 6 Years	1(2.8)	12(33.3)	23(63.9)	36(100.0)
Total	5(6.0)	33(39.3)	46(54.8)	84(100.0)

DISCUSSION:

There was a general lack of information on caries and oral hygiene in children with cleft, especially in children with cleft. This study provided an initial insight into this topic. This study is expected to make a useful contribution to the limited data on the oral health of children with clefts. The results of this study will also serve as a basis for future comparisons and help in planning preventive measures for these children¹⁰⁻¹¹. Studies conducted on caries experiments in young children with cleft lip and palate showed significant differences in their results. The present study showed a very extensive caries experience in both primary and mixed dentition. Our study results are in line with several other studies. It is known that the severity of caries and its incidence change with age. In the case of deciduous dentition, the effects cumulate until the age of 7, and then disappear as the decaying of deciduous teeth begins. Earlier studies on school-age and preschool children without clefts in Southern Punjab have found significantly lower levels of caries compared to the levels of caries in cleft children in this study. The high level of tooth decay in children with clefts can be attributed to little priority in dental care for these children, as parents focus on the numerous medical procedures necessary to correct birth defects in early childhood¹². Therefore, it is very

important to include dental prophylaxis regimens in the overall treatment protocol of these children. Our medical partners should be made aware of the relationship between CLP and dental health. Parents of split children should be informed about potential dental problems in their children and motivated to consult a dentist for better dental prophylaxis. The dentist also needs to be better informed about the special needs of children with clefts¹³⁻¹⁴. Oral rehabilitation programs must be designed with people with clefts in mind, which leads to better dental health. A coordinated team approach to treating all aspects of care should include close oversight of oral hygiene measures and constant professional maintenance through a system of regular lifelong referrals for people with cleft¹⁵. Parents of split children should be encouraged to make regular dental check-ups.

CONCLUSION:

The experience of caries in children with cleft lip and palate was very great. There was no significant difference between the experience of caries in children depending on their age and gender. Most children with clefts had good or either bad oral hygiene.

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